

Review Paper

Evaluation and formulation of the Herbal Lip Balm

Kadu Abhijeet*, Shelke Akash

Shri swami samarth institute of pharmacy malwadi,bota

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 05 Feb. 2025

Keywords:

Lip Balm, Natural
Ingredients, Spreadability

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14812469

ABSTRACT

The present research work is based on the formulation and evaluation of herbal lip balm by using natural herbals like rose oil, bees wax, Shea butter, vitamin E, Beet root. Rose oil nourishes and softens lips naturally. The herbal lip balm which possesses antiinflammatory properties and heals chapped lips was formulated and evaluated. The lip balm was produced by homogenous mixing. The lip balm, was characterized for physical stability, pH, melting point, and spreadability. The pH was found to be 5.5 to 6.5 and the melting point was found to be 63 to 65°C. After carrying out stability tests at room temperature (25.0-30.0°C) and in a refrigerator (4.0-2.0°C), it was demonstrated that the manufactured lip balm was uniform in nature and could be applied flawlessly without any deformation

INTRODUCTION

Lip Balm:

Lip Balm Is An A Cosmetic Product Which Is Used To The Most Sensitive Part Of The Body" Lips". The Skin Of The Lips Is Thin & Entirely Sensitive Suceptible To Irritation Prone To Attract Problems. Cosmetics Have Been In Use For A Thousand Of Year, With Ancient Egyptians & Sumerions Luring Them Regardless Of The Changes In Social Attitudes Towards Cosmetic Ideals Of Appearance Were Occasionally Achieved Using Cosmetics.

Lip anatomy

It is made up of the mucous membrane, areolar tissue, orbicularis muscle, superficial fascia, and skin. Dry, red mucous membrane that is continuous with the skin and has many touch corpuscles and vascular papillae covering the lip edges.

*Corresponding Author: Kadu Abhijeet

Address: Shri swami samarth institute of pharmacy malwadi,bota

Email ✉: abhijeetkadu820@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Fig. Lip Balm

Vermillion border

Latin terms labium superius oris and labium inferius oris refer to the anatomical names for the upper and lower lip, respectively. The lower lip includes the area between the lateral commissures and the labiomental crease of the chin, although considerations of the lips are typically focused on the vermilion zone. The upper lip extends from the nasolabial folds to the inferior border of the nose.

Tubercles

The tubercle or procheilon is the underlying fleshy fullness of the philtrum, which forms the downward arch of the cupid's bow.

Oral commissures

The commissure is the point where the upper and lower lips meet at the mouth angle.

Several muscles used in lip movement attach at this location.

Philtrum

A symmetrical pair of paramedian vertical philtral ridges that surround the philtrum, a central depression, are features of the upper lip. Dermal collagen and thick elastic tissue combine to generate a special collection that forms the philtrum and philtral ridges. It is thought that the philtrum provides extra skin that can be pulled into oral movements that need upper lip stretching.

CLASSIFICATION:

The Cosmetics May Be Classified In To 4 Main Groups Namely

1. Cosmetics For Skin
2. Cosmetics For Hair

3. Cosmetics For Nails
4. Cosmetics For Hygiene (Dental Care. Bathing Etc)

A Cosmetics For The Skin:

The Skin Covers Vast Area Of The Body. Lip Balm Is The Cosmetic Which Comes Under The Cosmetics For The Skin. Cosmetics Are Applied To Many Parts The Most Important Part Is The Face. The Skin Cosmetics Are Formulated In The Form Of Solids, Semi-Solids, Liquids, Solid Contains Powder & The Semi-Solids May Be Emulsion Or Simple Admixture. And The Liquid Contains Both The Monophasic And Biphasic Liquids.

Drug & Cosmetics Act, 1940:

- The Drugs & Cosmetic Act, 1940 Is An Act Of The Parliament Of The India Which Regulates The Import Manufacture & Distribution Of Drugs In India.
- The Primary Objective Of The This Drug & Cosmetic Act 1940 Is To Ensure That The Drugs & Cosmetics Sold In India. Are Safe, Effective & Conform To State Quality Standard.
- The Original Act Was Prepared In The Accordance With The Recommendation Of The Chopra Committee Formed in the 1930. The Related Drug Rules Was Passed In 1945. Since 1940, The Act Has Undergone Several Amendments and Is Now Known as The Drug & Cosmetic Act 1940.

Types of Lip Balm:

There Are Mainly 7 Kinds of The Lip Balm Which Are as Follows

1. Tinted Lip Balm.
2. Medicated Lip Balm
3. Flavoured Lip Balm.
4. Organic Lip Balm.
5. SPF Lip Balm
6. Plumping Lip Balm.
7. CBD Or Hemp Oil Lip Balm.

1. Tinted lip balm.

This Is the Type of The Lip Balm. Which Is Used to Hydrate & Colorize the Lips Which Is Called as Tinted. if The User Is Uncomfortable with The Heavy Cooking of The Lipsticks Then the Tinted Lip Balms Are Perfect Altern- a have, Many Users Uses The Tinted Lip Balm to Moisturize Their Lips as Well as To Give Them A Brilliant Wash of Color. It Is Very Easy to Use. Just Apply the Colored Lip Balm Directly to The Lips to Use It.

2. Medicated Lip Balm

This Lip Balms Are the Most Likely. To Be the Least Soothing & Irritating Lip Balms Amongst the Other Lip Balms. This Lip Balm Is Usually Prescribed by Dermatologist in A Medication for The Treatment Of The Chopped Lips & Other Conditions Regarding The Lips.

3. Flavoured Lip Balm

This Are the Lip Balms Which Consist of The Flavours Inside Them. Flavoured Lip Balms Are the Lip Balms That Are Added with Flavours Such as Vonilla, Mint, Mango & Many More Fruity Flavours. This Lip Balm Is Mode for Moisturizing.

4. Organic Lip Balm.

The Organic Lip Balm Is Kind of Lip Balm Which Have the Organic Or Natural Ingredients. In Other Lip Balms Which Have Chemical Ingredient That May Harm Lips and Skin, The Organic Lip Balm Is Usually Made from The Organic Ingredient Such As A Vocody Ail, Jojoba Oil, Bees Wax, Vitamin E Hemp, And Coca Butter. The Organk Lip Balm. Still Functions Of A Other Lip Balm. Which Provides Moisture & Protection from Dry F Chapped Lip

Raw materials-

Sr. No	Ingredient	Quantity	Uses
1.	Bees Wax	12%	Import A Lossing AndHardness
2.	Beetroot	11%	Colouring Agent
3.	Almond Oil	5%	Moisturizing Agent
4.	Aloe-Vera	4%	Antioxidant, Anti_ Inflammantory
5.	Vitamin-E	1.5%	Anti-Oxidant, Maintain The Stability
6.	Rose Water	2%	Flovouring Agent
7.	Glycerol	2 To 10%	Glossy Effect

CONCLUSION

The stability of the formulations kept in the refrigerator and at room temperature was comparable. Spreadability and stable organoleptic characteristics are regarded as "good." The product's functioning is preserved, thus storage under these circumstances is deemed appropriate. A lip balm composed of natural materials had a suitable melting temperature of 64° C on average during the stability test. In contrast to standard stability testing, the spreadability test indicates that furnace storage conditions (40.0±2.0° C) are not advised since they result in a loss of product functioning. Natural ingredient-based lip balms

were shown to be safe to use, and this combination was thought to be a superior option for lip balm formulation. It is possible to produce a new formulation with distinct and enhanced properties by altering the excipients or other excipient combinations. can produce a novel formulation with enhanced and unique properties. It is anticipated that this formula will stay constant based on recent research

REFERENCES

1. Christopulos A. Mouth anatomy Sep 11, 2018.
2. B.H. Ali, N.A. Wabel, G. Blunden, Phytochemical, pharmacological and

- toxicological aspects of *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L.: a review. *Phytother Res.* 19 (2005) 369-375,
3. 12. M.S. Balsam, E. Sagarin, *Cosmetics science and technology*, Second ed. Wiley Interscience Publication, NY, USA, 2008, 3. pp. 209-512.
 4. Fernandes AR, Dario MF, Stability evaluation of organic lip balm. *Brazilian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2013; 49: 293-300.
 5. Kadu M, Singh V. Review on natural lip balm *International Journal of Research in Cosmetic Science* 2015; (1): 1-7.
 6. Mayuri Kadu, Dr Suruchi Vishwasrao, and Dr Sonia Singh, A Review on Natural Lip Balm. *International Journal of Research in Cosmetic Science*. 03 August 2014. ISSN 22777172.
 7. A.R. Fernandes, M.F. Dario, C.A.S.O. Pinto, T.M. Kaneko, A.R. Baby, M.V.R. Velasco, Stability evaluation of organic Lip Balm, *Braz, J. Pharm. Sci.* 2 (2013) 49.
 8. Savalkar M.B. et al. Formulation & Evaluation of Herbal lipstick using *Amaranthus dubius*, *J. Pharm. Res.*, 2018, 7(6), 96-98.
 9. P. L. Kole, H. R. Jadhav, P. Thakurdesai, A. N. Nagappa, Cosmetic products of herbal extracts, *Natural Product Radiance*. 4 (2005) 4.
 10. Grindlay D. Reynolds T. The Aloe vera phenomenon: A review of the properties and modern uses of the leaf parenchyma gel. *J Ethnopharmacol.* 1986; 16:117-51.
 11. Kokate CK, Purohit AP, Gokhale SB. *Textbook of Pharmacognosy*, 49th ed. Pune: Nirali Prakashan, 2014.
 12. Mona Patel, Ojash Patel, formulation and evaluation of herbal lipstick using beta vulguris extract. *International ayurvedic medical journal*. June 2021.
 13. S. Deshmukh, M. Chavan, M. Sutar, S. Singh, Preparation and evaluation of natural lipsticks from *bixa orellana* seeds, *Int J Pharm Bio Sci.* 4 (2013) 139-144.
 14. GOUVEA, M.C.B.L.F. *Desenvolvimento de base de batons*. *Cosmet. Toiletries* (Portuguese edition), v.5, n.2, p.49-56, 1993.
 15. Sharma PP, *cosmetics- Formulation, manufacturing and quality control*, Edn 5. Vandana publications, Delhi, 2008, 297-313.
 16. H. Ratih, H. Titta, C.P. Ratna, Formulation of Cananga Oil Lip Balm as Emolient". *Prosiding Simposium Penelitian Bahan Obat Alami (SPBOA) XIV dan Muktamar XII PERHIPBA* 2014. Yogyakarta: Leutikaprio. p. 3, 2014.
 17. P.P. Sharma, "Cosmetics-Formulation, manufacturing and quality control", fourth ed. (2008). Vandana Publications Pvt. Ltd., India.
 18. H. I. N. Nasution, "Formulation of Lip Balm using Combination of Palm Kernel Oil (PKO) and Red Palm Oil (RPO) as Lip Moisturizer," Final project, Universitas Sumatera Utara, 2018.
 19. BRASIL. Ministério da Saúde. Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária. Séries Temáticas: Qualidade 1. Guia de Estabilidade de produtos cosméticos. Brasília, v.1, 2004. 45 p.
 20. OLIVEIRA, F.O. Contribuição da análise térmica no desenvolvimento de formulações de batons. São Paulo, 2003. 85 p. [Dissertation of Master degree. Institute of Chemistry. University of São Paulol.

HOW TO CITE: Kadu Abhijeet*, Shelke Akash, Evaluation and formulation of the Herbal Lip Balm, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 2, 343-346. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14812469>

